
INGLIZ, O‘ZBEK VA QORAQALPOQ TILLARIDAGI QISHLOQ XO‘JALIGI TERMINALOGIYASINING LEKSIK - SEMANTIK XUSUSIYATILARI

Abdullayev Sh.D

O‘razboyev O.R

Qoraqalpoq davlat universiteti

Annotation: The purpose of this article is to increase the linguistic features (similarities and similarities) of the agricultural terms used in the field of plant science in the Uzbek and Karakalpak languages, as well as the ways of forming (becoming) the terms. and is to determine methods of translation into English.

Key words: English language, Uzbek language, agriculture, terminology, lexicon, semantics, words.

ЛЕКСИКО-СЕМАНТИЧЕСКАЯ ХАРАКТЕРИСТИКА СЕЛЬСКОХОЗЯЙСТВЕННОЙ ТЕРМИНОЛОГИИ В АНГЛИЙСКОМ, УЗБЕКСКОМ И КАРАКАЛПАКСКОМ ЯЗЫКАХ

Abstract: The purpose of this article is to increase the linguistic features (similarities and similarities) of agricultural terms used in the field of crop production in the Uzbek languages, as well as the methods of formation (formation) of terms and the English language. methods of translation into language.

Key words: English language, Uzbek language, agriculture, terminology, vocabulary, semantics, words.

ЛЕКСИКО-СЕМАНТИЧЕСКАЯ ХАРАКТЕРИСТИКА СЕЛЬСКОХОЗЯЙСТВЕННОЙ ТЕРМИНОЛОГИИ В АНГЛИЙСКОМ, УЗБЕКСКОМ И КОРАКАЛПОКСКОМ ЯЗЫКАХ

Аннотация: Целью данной статьи является увеличение языковых особенностей (сходства и сходства) сельскохозяйственных терминов, используемых в области растениеводства в узбекском и каракалпакском языках, а также способов образования (становления) терминов и. заключается в определении методов перевода на английский язык.

Ключевые слова: английский язык, узбекский язык, сельское хозяйство, терминология, лексика, семантика, слова.

Uzbekistan Republic his own socio - economic development new industry On stage step put And our country world in society prestige And place increased In this regard, the First President I.A. Karimov expressed the following thoughts on this matter:

“It should be noted that, as part of the implementation of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Education” and the National Personnel Training Program, a comprehensive system of teaching foreign languages has been created, that is, a harmoniously matured system. created with the aim of forming an intelligent, modern, sharpened young generation, further integration of the republic into the world community - the provision of methodological materials requires further improvement. In ensuring the competitiveness and sustainable development of the economy of Uzbekistan, agriculture, considered one of the main industries, is one of the most important factors in the effective use of land, water, material, technical and labor resources, the organization of innovative agro-technological production in agriculture and increasing its competitiveness. From this point of view, one of the important areas is considered to be lexical-semantic features and the study of the translation of crop production terms in English, Uzbek and Karakalpak languages, which are the basis of agriculture. In Europe, research on comparative linguistics began in the first quarter of the 19th century, while in the East, especially in Uzbek and Karakalpak linguistics, it began much earlier, in the 11th century. For example, we can clearly see this in the work “Mukhokamat ul lug'atain”. In this work, A. Navoi further developed and improved the science of comparative

linguistics. Improving the processes of building a democratic state and a legal society has accelerated the active introduction into the lexicon of the Uzbek language of terms in the field of agriculture and crop production, which are the economic pillar of any state. This situation certainly provides an opportunity to develop terminology in this area. With the help of translation linguistics, attention is paid to a number of linguistic, lexical and semantic features of the use of English in our national language. The daily increase in environmental problems in agriculture shows the need for a more in-depth study of the field of crop production and the importance of exchanging experience with world scientists. In particular, by studying the theoretical and practical issues of dividing the vocabulary of the terminological system of plant growing into semantic microfields and studying term-like schemes from the lexicographic point of view of the English-Uzbek and Karakalpak languages, when translating terms from a foreign language to our national one, a comprehensive system of terminological research has been created, the study of semantic fields did not find its research as a specific monographic source. The solution to this problem shows the need to further improve the quality of a special bilingual (English-Uzbek) dictionary and dictionary of agricultural terms and compile a new English-Uzbek-Karakalpak dictionary of agricultural terms. There are terms that have not found their solution in terminology, that is, terms that in translation are not called purely Uzbek and purely Karakalpak terms, and today this issue is awaiting its solution. This article on the topic “Lexico-semantic features of agricultural terminology in English, Uzbek and Karakalpak languages” is the first step towards solving pressing problems awaiting such a solution. In the speech of President Shavkat Mirziyev at an extended meeting of the Cabinet of Ministers, dedicated to the main results of the socio-economic development of our country in 2016 and the most important priorities of the economic program for 2017, a number of strategically important tasks were set. In the development of agriculture in 2017, the implementation condition was determined. When implementing these urgent tasks, foreign experience will certainly be studied, and this automatically means the arrival of new terms in the domestic agricultural sector, and such reforms require the

development of field terminology in the Uzbek language. Because as a result of the development of tourist relations with foreign countries in a market economy, improvement of the ecological environment of our national tourist cities and at the same time changing environmental conditions on earth, there is undoubtedly a need for further enrichment of the gene pool of agricultural plants, taking into account the fact that expeditions to foreign countries are carried out at the Research Institute of Plant Growing In order to use the best practical experience of world scientists, first of all, it is necessary to study the terms of crop production and become familiar with their content. Currently, the plant gene bank of the Plant Growing Research Institute stores about one hundred species of crops and about 30 thousand seed samples. This gene pool is invaluable considering that the seeds of the surviving specimens were collected from around the world over the past 90 years and yet were completely lost in their homeland. The gene pool of plant science and the number of terms that form its basis are expanding and increasing every day under the influence of internal and external factors. However, most of the terms used in the field of crop production do not have equivalents in the Uzbek and Karakalpak languages. In the field of plant science, the meaning of embodied words is expressed through terms. In particular, in the field of plant growing, along with its own terms, there are also terms that came from other sciences and fields. If we turn to history, then the terms of plant growing have come to us from ancient times to the present day with a number of lexical-semantic and phonetic changes. The development of science and technology, production is also reflected in the language. This is especially true for terminology. Within the terminological system of plant growing, conducting research from the point of view of three (English, Uzbek and Karakalpak) languages is one of the new directions of Uzbek and Karakalpak linguistics, and much remains to be done in this area. . In Uzbekistan, a comprehensive study of the terminological system of plant growing is one of the yet unexplored issues from the point of view of the translation aspect of cognitive linguistics, in particular, the lexical and semantic features of translation from a foreign language into our language. National language. Below we will focus on several agricultural terms that have been adopted from English into

Uzbek.

Anorganic -anoorganik

Anther -changdon

Antirrhinum [,æntɪ'raɪnəm] itog'iz

Aphides - shira, o'simlik biti.

aphis -n shira, o'simlik biti.

arable - 1) haydalma yer; 2) chopiq; 2. v haydamoq.

arachnid - o'rgimchaksimonlar.

Bacterium- bakteriya, mikrob.

badlands - unumsiz yerlar.

badness - yaroqsizlik

bag [bæg] 1. n 1) qop, sumka; 2. v 1) qopga solmoq; 2) o'roq bilan o'rmoq.

bagger - n suv havzalarini chuqurlashtirib loy balchiqlarni chiqarib tashlaydigan mashina

camomile - n bot. moychechak

campanula - n bot. qo'ng'iroqgul

campestral - a dalaga oid

candytuft - soyabongullilar.

cane - 1. n qamish; 2. v xivchin bilan savalamoq, urmoq.

cane-brake -qamishzor

cane-sugar-shakarqamish.

canker - 1. n qurt tushgan joy, qurt teshgan, yegan joy; 2. v o'ymoq, kemirmoq.

cannabic -nasha o'simligiga oid, kanopdan qilingan.

Cantoloup- kantalupa (qovun navi).

Cany- qamishdan qilingan.

In conclusion, it should be noted that this topic is analyzed for the first time. However, foreign terminologists and translators have completed candidate and doctoral dissertations on various terminological topics of the Uzbek, Karakalpak and

English lexicons. It is known that as human society develops, the need of people to study their native language and other foreign languages naturally increases. Also, the changes taking place in our cultural life have a positive effect on human thinking. Integration processes have deeply affected the information and communication system, science, art, sports and almost all areas of production, increasing people's desire to study and master foreign languages more deeply. This serves as a direct impetus to the needs, aspirations and interests of students pursuing education in the field of agriculture.

References:

1. Сосюр Ф.Де. Труды по языкознанию. – М.: Прогресс, 1977. – 285 с.
2. Хижняк СП.Юридическая терминология: формирование и состав.– Саратов,1997. – 137с.
3. Пиголкин А.С. Язык закона. – М. 1990. – 85 с.
4. Милославская Д. И. Типовые трудности семантической интерпретации юридического текста Узбекский язык в его естественном и юридическом бытии. – Барнаул: Изд-во АГУ,2000. 272 с.
5. Lexical-semantic features of the terminology of agriculture in English and Uzbek languages Murodova Shakhnoza Chorievna, independent researcherUzbek State World Languages University